

Research and development publication of FITOFORCE Kutató és Fejlesztő Betéti Társaság

Project title: Critical content investigation of raw wastes from the fruit and vegetable processing industry, development of a new health-preserving product family from valuable wastes based on the test results

Project number: GINOP-2.1.7-15-2016-00874

Place of implementation: H-4481 Nyíregyháza, Sövény u.4/C.

Project closing date: 31 March 2020

Development manager: BARTUS Pál, development engineer

Short description of the research and development project:

We carried out the critical investigation of the wastes, generated during fruit and vegetable processing, using applied research methods. We searched for and evaluated the biologically active substances in the wastes, which were valuable from a nutritional aspect. Based on the results, we selected the wastes that can be best utilized and contain the most valuable biologically active substances: the waste generated during tomato pureeing, apple pressing and cherry pitting. We subjected them to further investigation based on product manufacturing aspects. The most promising waste produced during apple processing is apple pomace. Using apple pomace, we developed two new food supplements. For product development, we designed a manufacturing technology process that has not existed before, and we developed the technology as well. The production of new products required technical development, we carried out the development and design of the new and modified production equipment adapted to the product. We developed and produced two marketable prototypes. One is the production of apple fibre capsules from apple pomace. The wet apple pomace required drying at a special low temperature in order to preserve the contents, then it was finely ground under special refrigerated conditions and the grinding with the appropriate micro-particle size was encapsulated. The production of the special micro grinding, the most useful formula from a nutritional point of view, is very important here. The raw material of our second product is the special apple fibre micro grinding. Using apple fibre, we created an edible product with a pleasant texture and taste, the apple fibre biscuit. We experimented and produced the apple fibre biscuit in two versions: the first version was prepared with wheat flour and the second version was gluten-free. The ingredients, recipe and production technology of the biscuits are confidential, and we intend to patent them. The products (5 samples) were tested in an accredited food industry laboratory and received the appropriate certification.

Description of the development process of the prototype:

During the implementation period of the project, we carried out the following activities for the purpose of development, in order to produce prototype products:

1. Critical investigation

We counted the wastes generated during processing in fruit and vegetable processing plants, namely in 7 canneries. We took samples from the significant amount and relatively pure homogeneous wastes and prepared those for the tests. We evaluated the samples from a nutritional point of view as well as from the point of view of further processing. Based on the tests, we selected the wastes

classified as valuable and suitable for the development purpose. The three most promising wastes selected are the following: pureeing residue from tomato processing, apple pomace left after crushing and juice extraction of apples, and cherry pits produced during cherry pitting. We subjected these wastes to further investigation based on product manufacturing aspects. The most promising waste generated during apple processing turned out to be apple pomace. Apple pomace is available in large quantities in a homogeneous state free of contamination from other substances, therefore during product development, this waste formed the raw material for further development.

2. Technology development and its elaboration

The selected raw material was prepared for further development in the first phase. We developed a gentle drying technology to ensure that the valuable contents do not change, damage, or transform due to heat input. During the physical preparation of the food that can be consumed and is best utilized by the human body, we tried several grinding technologies, since according to literature, micro grinding is the one that is best utilized in the human body. The production of micro grinding is a heat-generating process, the grinding can easily overheat and be damaged, so it was necessary to experiment and develop a grinding technology under cooled conditions.

By producing the micro grinding, we produced a product that is already suitable for human consumption, with a pleasant texture and taste, which was confirmed by the later accredited laboratory test.

The micro grinding is already available and can be mixed into drinks, shakes, and other food products. In order to facilitate consumption and dosage, we produced an apple fibre powder product in capsule form, which is the first prototype product of our development project.

The second prototype product, after several failed attempts (apple fibre chocolate, apple fibre drink, apple fibre puree), became the apple fibre biscuits. This product is also a pleasant-tasting, easy-to-eat food, which is also supported by an accredited laboratory test. Two versions were prepared of this: normal and gluten-free for gluten intolerants.

3. Development of the production technology required to produce commercial quantities

The two finished prototype products, the apple fibre capsule and the apple fibre biscuit, were prepared under laboratory conditions, therefore it became necessary to develop a production technology capable of producing commercial quantities. During the development of technologies, we defined as a basic criterion the search for the simplest possible solution, as well as the production based on machines and equipment manufactured in the food machinery industry.

The developed production technology is suitable to produce both products with different endpoints in the production. The recipe of the products and the production technology are considered business secrets, and we wish to patent them.

4. Preparation for the market launch of the two products produced by the development

The market appearance, packaging, brand name and design of the two prototype products were planned. The representative demand was assessed, the products were positioned, and the target market was designated. Market forecasts and consumer behaviour were analysed, and the consumer structure was determined. In relation to the company and the developed products, an examination of the company's own characteristics was carried out with the help of a SWOT analysis. The expected market share was determined, the competitor analysis was prepared. We carried out a marketing

mix analysis. We defined the communication related to the products and prepared the promotional programmes.

Summary

International research results prove the beneficial effects of vegetables and fruits on human health and the importance of the biologically active substances of vegetables and fruits in eliminating harmful free radicals. Serious public health problems can primarily be influenced by changing dietary habits, increasing the consumption of fruit and vegetables, and consuming food supplements made of fruit and vegetables. The two new products created by our development project are the result of the processing of cheap, nutritionally valuable, natural vegetable and fruit waste materials of the canning industry. We developed new products using materials that until now have been used in landfills, or at best in composters and a very small percentage as animal feed. The products developed by us will be available to a wide range of people due to their relatively low price. The consumption of our developed products primarily provides an adequate solution to digestive problems, which are considered common diseases. One of the main causes of the development of digestive problems, diseases of the stomach and intestines is insufficient dietary fibre intake. The regular consumption of the developed apple fibre capsule and the apple fibre biscuit as a food supplement naturally replaces the fibre substances that would not otherwise be taken in. Our developed products can have a direct impact on the health preservation of consumers.